

The formation of massive close binaries: is the migration scenario viable?

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In contrast to the low- and intermediate-mass stars, star formation in its high-mass ($M_{init} > 8 M_{\odot}$) regime is still very uncertain. The formation of young massive stars occurs embedded in their obscured natal clouds and is rapid, making observing them very challenging. In addition, it is now known that most massive stars experience multiplicity (presence of one -or more- stellar companion(s)) even during their earliest phases [1, 2]. Multiplicity scales with mass and reaches almost 100% for main sequence OB stars, a fact that cannot be omitted while studying the early stages of massive stars. A large fraction of massive stars appear to host at least one *close* companion (< 1 au), meaning that the most likely end product of massive star formation is a rather close binary (or higher-order system). An important question to be addressed by the community is how these multiples were formed. It is likely that they were initially born as a wide system that evolved into a tighter one, the consequence of an inward migration of the companion(s) [3]. Understanding high-mass multiple star formation in detail would simplify the predictions of their final fate, as for example core collapse supernova or gamma ray bursts. Observational studies of massive young binaries, either at the Massive Young Stellar Object (MYSO) or pre-main sequence stage are essential to gather information about the various formation theories in place.

Up to now, numerous high-resolution imaging studies have been conducted to explore the early multiplicity of young stars probing relatively large separations (from ~ 500 to $\sim 15\,000$ au). However, little is known about the close environment (< 100 au) of massive forming stars. In these proceedings, I summarise the analysis published in [4], where we bring novel observational constraints about the multiplicity of six young massive stars (1 – 100 au) in the M17 nearby star-forming region and discuss the most likely channels for the formation of such multiple systems.

The M17 sample

Long baseline near infrared interferometry enables to spatially resolve binaries and get unique astrometric information. In particular, the GRAVITY instrument at the VLTI is able to detect rather close and faint companions down to ~ 1 mas and $\Delta\text{mag}=4$. Our sample consists of six young O stars in the M17 complex, the brightest ones in the region and for which reliable measurements of the radial velocities and well defined spectral types are available in the literature (Figure 1). We obtain six snapshot observations along with six medium resolution spectra ($R\sim 500$) with GRAVITY. The acquisitions were preceded by the observations of a point-source calibration star, close to the target physically and in terms of spectral type, to accurately correct the atmospheric and

instrumental transfer function.

Figure 1: Digitized Sky Survey (DSS) image on which the M17 GRAVITY sources are labelled in white.

Methods

The main interferometric observables, the visibility amplitudes ($|V|$) and closure phases (CP) were modelled using the python module PMOIRE. From the $|V|$ and CP, we derive the variable parameters of flux ratio (f) and the source positions ($\Delta\alpha; \Delta\beta$) by performing binary model fitting. Binaries produce two fringe packets that will overlap to produce a sinusoidal signal in the visibility amplitudes. The separation between the peaks relates to the binary separation while the minimum visibility provides a measurement of the flux ratio between components. The CPs are sensitive to the asymmetries in the source distribution. A variety of models has been explored for each source, iteratively increasing the multiplicity order (single, binary, triple...) and complexity (e.g fully resolved component). We infer the mass of the objects comparing the calibrated K -band spectra to a family of atmosphere models and evolutionary tracks (the full method can be found in [4]).

Results - Multiplicity and companion fraction

We find that 100% of the targeted sources host at least one companion in the probed separation range (1-100 mas): three are binaries and three are triples. When adding the five spectroscopic companions reported in the literature, a total of 14 companions orbit the six systems yielding a companion fraction (CF) of 2.3 ± 0.6 (see Fig-

ure 2). These observational results are compatible with the multiplicity fractions (MF) and CFs measured in other galactic regions for stars with $M > 20 M_{\odot}$ [1, 5, 6]. The young age of M17 and the cluster environment tends to show that massive star formation results in a multiple system with at least two companions on average.

Figure 2: MF and CF measured with GRAVITY for the six O-stars in M17 (red) as a function of the primary mass. For reference, values of other studies are also presented for different primary mass ranges. For a given symbol, the black marker stands for the companion fraction while the plain color refers to the multiplicity fraction.

Results - Separation distribution and mass ratio

The detected interferometric companions span a wide range of separations, ranging from 1 mas to ~ 70 mas. Two companions were found at very close distances (around 1 mas), five are located at intermediate separations ($4 < a < 20$ mas) and one is relatively distant (~ 70 mas). Similarly, we investigate the brightness properties. Flux ratios are converted into brightness contrasts and displayed as a function of the companion separation. Again, no clear trend can be identified and rather shows the contrasting companion profiles. There is a gap in the

signal with a significant lack of detection below $\Delta \text{mag} \sim 2$ for companions located within 3 mas, which are ambitious sensitivities to reach with GRAVITY. Overall, these results show the broad variety of companions surrounding these pre-main sequence massive stars.

Consequences for the star formation scenario

A successful model for massive star formation should reproduce the proximity between the components and the high-degree of multiplicity observed in older populations of massive stars. To date, only two main theoretical approaches were explored to support massive star formation: monolithic collapse of turbulent cores and competitive accretion. Lately, it has been shown evidence for an inward migration of stars as a function of a cluster age, one of the numerous processes that can favour the hardening of binaries [7]. While this mechanism can occur in both theories, collaborators suggest that massive binaries are formed in wide pairs and then evolve into tight systems following a timescale of ~ 2 Myrs [8, 7]. Detecting companions within 2 mas from the primary star in M17 could indicate that protostellar cores formed at the edges of the accretion disk migrated over time and are entering the spectroscopic regime, as suggested by Oliva [9] and Ramírez-Tannus [7]. Additionally, the presence of companions at wider distances (dozens of mas) is also a valid detection featuring the migration process. In fact, disk fragmentation occurring in the vicinity of the central forming star may boost the formation of prestellar cores at similar distances (~ 100 au) [9]. Given the young age of M17 (~ 1 Myr), a combination of mechanisms is at play to set the final structures of the cluster. We seek to investigate whether such behaviour extends to the youngest and faintest objects in the region, confirming or discrediting the proposed scenario. If the migration scenario is correct, we expect that most of the objects have at least one detectable companion within the expected size of the accretion disk. A non-detection of companions within ~ 200 au would invalidate the migration scenario.

References

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Short CV

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